

Laboratory-scale cultivation tests for nutrient-saturated biochars

The tests were performed by BZN within Task 4.4 (Activated Biochar as Adsorbent). The results are included in D4.5: Advanced Use of Biochar for Nutrient Retention.

Methodology

The saturation process of the different biochars was done at BZN to ensure that the chars were fully loaded. Four types of biochar were received from VTT and used in the experiments:

- plant biochar ('Pflanzenkohle' / Sonnenerde GmbH) - original
- manure biochar ('Güllekohle' / CharLine) - original
- plant biochar ('Pflanzenkohle' / Sonnenerde GmbH) - activated by VTT
- manure biochar ('Güllekohle' / CharLine) - activated by VTT

Loading (saturation) of biochar was carried out according to the method provided by VTT, having a substrate-to-solution ratio of 1:25. Three 5-gram aliquots of each biochar sample were added to 125 ml of 25 mg/l KNO_3 , NH_4Cl or KH_2PO_4 solutions, in order to load the biochar with potassium, nitrogen and phosphorus, respectively. The solutions were mixed with a circular shaker for 24 hours (*Figure 1*). Biochar samples were filtered from the solutions with filter paper and dried at room temperature before the pot experiments. The nutrient adsorption process of the biochar samples was monitored by measuring the pH and concentration of NH_4Cl , KH_2PO_4 and KNO_3 in the loading solutions.

Pot experiments were carried out with eight different samples: unsaturated and saturated samples of the four types of biochars. 1-gram aliquots of biochars were mixed into the top 2 cm layer of sandy soils in 7x7 cm pots (*Figure 2*).

Figure 1. Nutrient loading of biochars

Figure 2. Preparation of pot experiment with biochars

Two seeds of 'Lollo Bionda' lettuce were sown into each pot. Pots were watered and put under artificial light (8^{00} - 18^{00}). Four pots were used for each experimental setting and control without biochar. Germination of seeds was followed, and the number of leaves was recorded daily. The macronutrient (N, P, K) content of the soil and plant leaves was determined at the end of the experiment.

Results

Biochar saturation experiments

Figure 3 and Figure 7 present the pH values measured in loading solutions mixed with original and activated biochars, respectively. The effectivity of the nutrient adsorption process was monitored by comparing the macronutrient (N, P, K) content in the original loading solutions with the concentrations measured at the end of the 24 h saturation time. Figure 4-Figure 6 and Figure 8-Figure 10 present the results of the measurements with original and activated biochars, respectively. Changes in N, P, K content of the solutions used for the loading (saturation) process with original and activated biochars are summarised in Table 1 and Table 2, respectively.

Figure 3. pH of NH₄Cl, KH₂PO₄ and KNO₃ loading solutions before and after mixing with original biochars (NH₄Cl= original NH₄Cl solution; PNH₄Cl= NH₄Cl solution after mixing with original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar; GNH₄Cl= NH₄Cl solution after mixing with original 'Güllekohle' biochar; KNO₃= original KNO₃ solution, PKNO₃= KNO₃ solution after mixing with original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar; GKNO₃= KNO₃ solution after mixing with original 'Güllekohle' biochar; KH₂PO₄= original KH₂PO₄ solution; PKH₂PO₄= KH₂PO₄ solution after mixing with original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar, PKH₂PO₄= KH₂PO₄ solution after mixing with original 'Güllekohle' biochar)

Figure 4. Nitrogen content of NH₄Cl, KH₂PO₄ and KNO₃ solutions before and after mixing with original biochars (sample codes are explained in the caption of Figure 3)

Figure 5. Phosphorus content of NH₄Cl, KH₂PO₄ and KNO₃ solutions before and after mixing with original biochars (sample codes are explained in the caption of Figure 3)

Figure 6. Potassium content of NH₄Cl, KH₂PO₄ and KNO₃ solutions before and after mixing with original biochars (sample codes are explained in the caption of Figure 3)

Figure 7. pH of NH_4Cl , KH_2PO_4 and KNO_3 solutions before and after mixing with activated biochars (NH4Cl= original NH_4Cl solution, APNH4= NH_4Cl solution after mixing with activated 'Pflanzkohle' biochar, AGNH4= NH_4Cl solution after mixing with activated 'Güllekohle' biochar, KNO_3 = original KNO_3 solution, APNO3= KNO_3 solution after mixing with activated 'Pflanzkohle' biochar, AGNO3= KNO_3 solution after mixing with activated 'Güllekohle' biochar, KH_2PO_4 = original KH_2PO_4 solution, APPO4= KH_2PO_4 solution after mixing with activated 'Pflanzkohle' biochar, AGPO4= KH_2PO_4 solution after mixing with activated 'Güllekohle' biochar)

Figure 8. Nitrogen content of NH_4Cl , KH_2PO_4 and KNO_3 solutions before and after mixing with activated biochars (sample codes are explained in the caption of Figure 7)

Figure 9. Phosphorus content of NH_4Cl , KH_2PO_4 and KNO_3 solutions before and after mixing with activated biochars (sample codes are explained in the caption of Figure 7)

Figure 10. Potassium content of NH_4Cl , KH_2PO_4 and KNO_3 solutions before and after mixing with activated biochars (sample codes are explained in the caption of Figure 7)

Table 1. Changes in N, P, K content of the solutions used for the loading (saturation) process with original biochars. Cases where adsorption could be detected are highlighted with green letters.

Nutrient	The solution used for the loading process	Changes in the nutrient content of solutions after the loading (saturation) process	
		original 'Güllekohle' biochar	original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar
Nitrogen content (Figure 4)	NH_4Cl	decreased (adsorption occurred)	decreased (adsorption occurred)
	KNO_3	did not change (no adsorption occurred)	slightly increased (nutrients released from the biochar into the solution)
	KH_2PO_4	increased (nutrients released from the biochar into the solution)	increased (nutrients released from the biochar into the solution)
Phosphorus content	NH_4Cl	increased (nutrients released from the biochar)	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)

Nutrient	The solution used for the loading process	Changes in the nutrient content of solutions after the loading (saturation) process	
		original 'Güllekohle' biochar	original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar
(Figure 5)	KNO ₃	increased (nutrients released from the biochar)	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)
	KH ₂ PO ₄	decreased (adsorption occurred)	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)
Potassium content (Figure 6)	NH ₄ Cl	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)
	KNO ₃	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)
	KH ₂ PO ₄	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)

Table 2. Changes in N, P, K content of the solutions used for the loading (saturation) process with activated biochars. Cases where adsorption could be detected are highlighted with green letters.

Nutrient	The solution used for the loading process	Changes in the nutrient content of solutions after the loading (saturation) process	
		activated 'Güllekohle' biochar	activated 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar
Nitrogen content (Figure 8)	NH ₄ Cl	largely decreased (high adsorption occurred)	largely decreased (high adsorption occurred)
	KNO ₃	largely decreased (high adsorption occurred)	largely decreased (high adsorption occurred)
	KH ₂ PO ₄	increased (nutrients released from the biochar)	increased (nutrients released from the biochar)
Phosphorus content (Figure 9)	NH ₄ Cl	increased (nutrients released from the biochar)	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)
	KNO ₃	increased (nutrients released from the biochar)	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)
	KH ₂ PO ₄	decreased (adsorption occurred)	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)
Potassium content (Figure 10)	NH ₄ Cl	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)
	KNO ₃	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)
	KH ₂ PO ₄	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)	largely increased (high amount of nutrient released from the biochar)

Near neutral or slightly acidic pH of the nutrient solutions increased to the alkaline range after mixing with the original and activated biochars (*Figure 3* and *Figure 7*, respectively). All three nutrient solutions became highly alkaline after mixed with activated 'Güllekohle' biochar.

The results listed in Table 1 and Table 2 are summarised as follows:

- In most cases, nutrients were released from the biochar into the loading solution. This experience aligns with the results gained by VTT and ALCN in similar adsorption tests (see sections 2.4.1 and 2.4.3 in deliverable D4.7).
- In their original form, both 'Güllekohle' and 'Pflanzenkohle' biochars can adsorb ammonium-N, which capacity seems to be enhanced by the activation process so does the adsorption capacity towards nitrate-N, which could be detected only with the activated forms.
- Only 'Güllekohle' biochar could adsorb phosphate, and the activation process did not enhance this capacity.
- Potassium concentrations were two orders of magnitude higher in the solutions after the saturation process, especially in the case of activated 'Güllekohle' biochar, which increased the pH of the solution to 12. This phenomenon is probably due to the biochars' ash (KOH) content, which leads to a high level of potassium and hydroxide ion release.
- Based on comparing the results with original biochars and activated ones, the following conclusions can be drawn:
 - the activation process applied by VTT increased the adsorption capacity towards both ammonium and nitrate;
 - the activation process did not affect the adsorption capacity towards phosphate and potassium.

Pot experiments

In the first experiment, a comparison was made between plantless pots and pots containing growing plants to see how significant the nutrient uptake is from the soils and whether there were any nutrient limitations by the end of the experiments. Although some differences could be observed in some cases, there was no significant difference between the nutrient content of the plantless and the plant-containing soils (*Figure 11-Figure 13*).

Figure 11. Nitrogen content of soils at the end of the pot experiments with or without plants (K1=control 1, K2=control2, P= original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar mixed into the soil at a rate of 1 g/pot, G= original 'Güllekohle' biochar mixed into the soil at a rate of 1 g/pot. "-" signs indicate those pots that did not contain plants)

Figure 12. Phosphorus content of soils at the end of the pot experiments with or without plants (codes are explained in the caption of Figure 11)

Figure 13. Potassium content of soils at the end of the pot experiments with or without plants (codes are explained in the caption of Figure 11)

In the later experiments, only **soil nutrient content with growing plants was analysed**. The addition of unsaturated (original) (Figure 11-Figure 13) or saturated (Figure 14-Figure 16) original biochars did not have any positive effect on the macronutrient content of soils. The same results were obtained with the activated biochar versions as well.

Figure 14. Nitrogen content of soils at the end of the pot experiments with saturated biochars (K=control, PNO3= original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar saturated with nitrate, PPO4= original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar saturated with phosphate, PNH4= original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar saturated with ammonium, GNO3= original 'Güllekohle' biochar saturated with nitrate, GPO4= original 'Güllekohle' biochar saturated with

phosphate, GNH4= original 'Güllekohle' biochar saturated with ammonium mixed into the soil at a rate of 1g/pot.)

Figure 15. Phosphorus content of soils at the end of the pot experiments with saturated biochars (codes are explained in the caption of Figure 14)

Figure 16. Potassium content of soils at the end of the pot experiments with saturated biochars (codes are explained in the caption of Figure 14)

The plant leaves' nutrient (N, P, K) content was determined at the end of the experiments. The addition of neither unsaturated (Figure 17-Figure 19) nor saturated (Figure 20-Figure 22) original biochars positively affected the macronutrient content of plants grown in the amended soil medium. The same results were obtained with the saturated activated biochar versions (Figure 23-Figure 25).

Figure 17. Nitrogen content of plants at the end of the pot experiments with unsaturated original biochars (K1=control 1, K2=control2, P= original unsaturated 'Pflanzkohle' biochar, G= original unsaturated 'Güllekohle' biochar mixed into the soil at a rate of 1 g/pot.)

Figure 18. Phosphorus content of plants at the end of the pot experiments with unsaturated original biochars (codes are explained in the caption of Figure 17)

Figure 19. Potassium content of plants at the end of the pot experiments with unsaturated original biochars (codes are explained in the caption of Figure 17)

Figure 20. Nitrogen content of plants at the end of the pot experiments with saturated original biochars (K=control, PNO3= original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar saturated with nitrate, PPO4= original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar saturated with phosphate, PNH4= original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar saturated with ammonium, GNO3= original 'Güllekohle' biochar saturated with nitrate, GPO4= original 'Güllekohle' biochar saturated with phosphate, GNH4= original 'Güllekohle' biochar saturated with ammonium mixed into the soil at a rate of 1 g/pot.)

Figure 21. Phosphorus content of plants at the end of the pot experiments with saturated original biochars (codes are explained in the caption of Figure 20)

Figure 22. Potassium content of plants at the end of the pot experiments with saturated original biochars (codes are explained in the caption of Figure 20)

Figure 23. Nitrogen content of plants at the end of the pot experiments with saturated activated biochars (K=control, APNO3= activated 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar saturated with nitrate, APP04= activated 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar saturated with phosphate, APNH4= activated 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar saturated with ammonium, AGNO3= activated 'Güllekohle' biochar saturated with nitrate, AGPO4= activated 'Güllekohle' biochar saturated with phosphate, AGNH4= activated 'Güllekohle' biochar saturated with ammonium mixed into the soil at a rate of 1 g/pot.)

Figure 24. Phosphorus content of plants at the end of the pot experiments with saturated activated biochars (codes are explained in the caption of Figure 23)

Figure 25. Potassium content of plants at the end of the pot experiments with saturated activated biochars (codes are explained in the caption of Figure 23)

The addition of original biochars to soils in the plant cultivation experiments did not have any positive effect on the germination of seeds neither regarding the time of germination nor the number of germinated seeds (Figure 26). Similarly, none of the original unsaturated biochars had a significant positive effect on the leaf number of the plants (Figure 27). The same results were obtained with the saturated original and activated biochars.

Figure 26. Germination of lettuce 'Lollo Bionda' seeds in a pot experiment (K1=control 1, K2=control 2, P= original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar mixed into the soil at a rate of 1 g/pot, G= original 'Güllekohle' biochar mixed into the soil at a rate of 1 g/pot)

Figure 27. Average leaf number of lettuce 'Lollo Bionda' plants in a pot experiment (K1=control 1, K2=control2, P= original 'Pflanzenkohle' biochar mixed into the soil at a rate of 1 g/pot, G= original 'Güllekohle' biochar mixed into the soil at a rate of 1 g/pot)

The plant cultivation tests showed that none of the biochar samples (unsaturated/saturated original biochars, unsaturated/saturated activated biochars) had a significant effect on the soil and plant parameters (germination, average leaf number, soil nutrient content, and plant leaf nutrient content) investigated. A probable reason for this phenomenon is that the total amount of nutrients that could be released into the soil from the added biochars was not high enough to increase the already available nutrient content of the soil significantly.